

FACTORS AFFECTING SAUDI CONSUMERS' ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS THE USE OF ELECTRONIC PAYMENT

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of Electronic Payment (E-P) was aided by the global spread and usage of the internet and cell phones. In Saudi Arabia, there is a scarcity of research that offers a systematic synthesis and study of the factors influencing the utilize and acceptance of electronic payment approaches. E-P popularity has been reached out to a mass in Saudi Arabia which brings more research on its consumers. E-payment (E-P) have been widely accepted to a large number of consumers in Saudi, which brings a great demand of this sector, this research has been done to check over it, pros and cons. In view of the promising growth of e-payment in Saudi Arabia, the aim of the study is to discover the factors affecting e-payment acceptance from the perspective of Saudi consumers. Consumer adoption of e-payment is influenced by factors such as perceived protection, subjective standard, self-efficacy, ease of use, trust, and benefits, according to the literature. The link between the decision of an e-payment and the actual use of an e-payment is then investigated. A self-reporting survey has been created and distributed to 850 people, with 406 eligible statistical answers considered. According to the conclusions, only perceived easy use has a positive effect on perceived utility. According to the SPSS multi-regression study, gains, subjective standard, self-efficiency, and usage simplicity affect the perceptions of e-payment systems by Saudi consumers, whereas confidence and protection are not significantly related with e-payment systems perceptions by consumers. In addition, important coefficients were discovered

between e-payment acceptance by e-payment consumers and actual e-payment use. This research shows that e-payment acceptance and use, in Saudi Arabia, is now available. It has advanced knowledge. The implications of the results have been discussed further for e-payment system developers, policymakers, financial institutions, online providers, and software developers.

Keywords: Subjective Norm; Self-Efficacy; Perceived Security; Intention Electronic payment; Customers' perception; Saudi Arabia.

INTRODUCTION

As a way of conducting online transactions, e-payment have grown in popularity. In the area of e-commerce, new financial needs have been generated that conventional payment systems are often not able to meet efficiently. Internet development has helped to make this payment tool more popular (Sumanjeet, 2009; Alkhowaiter, 2020). Since then, different e-payment systems and vendors have arisen, increasingly in complexity with more complex e-commerce transactions. There are a number of disadvantages known to traditional e-payment systems that prevent clients from using them. According to previous research, all of these factors are connected with lack of trust, protection, usability, high transaction costs, lack of perceived advantage and risk. The fact that consumers use an online payment system is thought to be critical in these areas. Moreover, unless the payment systems meet these requirements, consumers will abandon online business, thereby making retailers lose their business in future online sales (Baabdullah et al., 2019; Abrashevich, 2004; Rana & Sulphrey, 2020). Security is one of the main e-payment concerns. This is because money and information are shared without direct contact with the beneficiaries via the Internet. Credit card fraud is the key source of concern in this region (Meuthia et al., 2020).

In other words, research into electronic, online, and mobile payments has revealed some common security issues, which are one of the major roadblocks to e-money adoption. The main cause of concern in the region is credit card fraud (Meuthia et al., 2020). Customers could face the risk of not being able to make payments due to insufficient infrastructure, the risk of personal data being misused, the risk of malicious parties committing fraud, and other risks (Coppolino et al., 2015; Widayat et al., 2020). Another significant factor that influences consumer trust in E-P s is perceived risk. Users are also concerned about their personal information and credit card numbers falling into the possession of hackers (Teoh et al., 2013). Furthermore, according to Hoffman et al., (1999) and Teoh et al., (2013) Hoffman et al. (1999), 95% of web users have declined to send personal information to websites, with 40% claiming that they would fabricate their missing data. Another significant factor for online applications is confidence in e-commerce transactions (Teoh et al., 2013; Shao et al., 2019). On e-commerce consumer decisions, perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived utility (PU) are also exempling of perceived benefit. Perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived utility (PU) on e-commerce consumer decision making to implement an E-P system are also examples of perceived benefit (Davis, 1989). The convenience that E-P s offer contributes to PU and PEOU by allowing transactions to be done with the least amount of time and money (Leong et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the usability aspect helps customers to enter user-friendly applications that are simple to navigate. The payment systems in Saudi Arabia have significantly changed over the past 15 years. The central bank (www.sama.gov.sa) of Saudi Central Bank SCB has led and continues to do so with cooperation and support for commercial banks in the creation and daily management of a modern national payments system to help the Kingdom evolve (Baabdullah et al., 2019; Rana & Sulphrey, 2020). Banks and their customers have gained significant advantages from this cooperation approach to building an effective and joint payment infrastructure that builds on advanced banking systems' best practices and innovations. The banks refused to invest expensively while their clients benefitted from the ease of use and connectivity of new payment services. SCB has established the main components of a fair and comprehensive system of electronic payments. The payment infrastructure includes a single electronic money transmission system for high value payments and direct debits on the same and forward date days as well as a national system for all ATMs and points of sale (SPAN) card and credit card transactions (SARIE). All Saudi banks participate in SWIFT and send and receive payment messages internationally through SWIFT. Saudi Arabia still have a large number of cash and check users, especially in the comparison to other leading cashless states, despite progress in E-P infrastructure. This indicates a higher cash use in Saudi Arabia, with many countries preferring to withdraw cash for point-of-sale transactions rather than using E-P services such as paying with a credit card. It is clear that, while E-P has gained greater acceptance in Saudi Arabia, it has not yet been completely used and accepted by all countries (sama.gov.sa, 2016; Alhanoof & Othman, 2018). As a result, it will be critical for comms to consider the main factors influencing E-P adoption across nations. To fully migrate to E-P, it will be necessary to understand the main factors affecting E-P adoption among nations.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 will comment on previous literatures related to the factors or variables studied, Section 3 will address the methodology and assumptions of this report, Section 4 will focus on the interpretation of findings, and finally, Section 5 will wrap up the paper and provide suggestions for future studies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definitions of E-Payment

An E-P system is a method of transactions or payment by electronic means for goods and services without check and cash. It is also known as a payment system electronic or online. Due to the growing spread of internet-based banking and shopping, the E-P system has expanded over the last few decades. The increasing number of E-P systems and payment processing devices can be seen in more technological development in the world. The percentage of check and cash transactions will fall as they increase, improve and offer ever more secure online payment transactions. E-P is one of the key features of e-banking since it concerns the financial exchange (Zhang & Jasimuddin, 2012; Widayat et al., 2020). It can also be used as a primary e-shopping

payment method, but not as a general rule for e-learning or other e-services where other payment methods are available.

Online ecommerce and E-P also play an important role, and the absence of an efficient system could hinder the development of e-commerce overall (Alkhowaiter, 2020; Teoh et al., 2013). The rapid development of the Internet has required the development of new web-based E-P systems than conventional payments (Panurach, 1996). Shon & Swatman, (1998) describes E-P as an electronic channel exchange of funds, whilst Gans & Scheelings, (1999) define it as electronic payouts connected to deposits or credit accounts by direct electronic signals. Any payment without a paper cheque in cash is called an E-P (Hord, 2005; Widayat et al., 2020). These definitions are used in the report and E-P defined as a transfer of electronic payment value from the payer to the payee by means of an E-P facility that allows clients to access bank accounts and transactions remotely and to manage them via an electronic network (Lim et al., 2006; Alkhowaiter, 2020). E-P requires internet connection to function like other e-environments, such as e-banking, electronic shopping, and electronic learning (e-learning).

E-Payment System Methods

In countries all over the world, a plethora of electronic payment methods have emerged to meet a variety of needs. As a result, many organizations have developed electronic payment methods in order to address the large number of online purchases and the security that must be in place to ensure their security (Meuthia et al., 2020). Secure credit card transactions, e-cash, electronic cheques, and online fund transfers are just a few of the EPS options. To provide the necessary infrastructure to allow payment over the Internet, E-P system methods are needed. They are rapidly becoming an integral part of, and are critical to, the advancement of electronic communications (Hord, 2005). They are becoming an increasingly important part of, and are critical for, the continued growth of electronic commerce and electronic business, and as a result, payment must have the following characteristics in order to be accepted globally. Atomicity must ensure that no current money is lost during the process and that the new transaction can be completed.

E-Payment in Saudi Arabia

In recent decades, the growth of their e-commerce activities in both developed and developing countries has been huge. Financial transactions/payments through the Internet are called e-commerce, for example via websites or mobile applications (Alzoubi, 2016). Global consumer online business (B2C), which accounts for 17% annually increased by 11% in the previous year, reached 1,84 trillion USD in 2017. Asia now represents half of worldwide online trading. China has the highest B2C share in Asia with a turnover of 681 billion dollars; the USA and the UK (US) are second and third worldwide with a market share of 438 billion dollars and 196 billion dollars in B2C (Rana & Sulphey, 2020; Alhanoof & Othman, 2018). B2C e-commerce in the Middle East is gaining traction, particularly in the UAE and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

(KSA) (Hamad et al., 2019). Saudi Arabia has the highest populations in six of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, comprising the United Arab Emirates, the United Kingdom, Kuwait, Bahrain, Oman and Qatar (Alkhowaiter, 2020; Alabdan, 2019). It is clearly seen that importance and the significance of E-P s over the years in Saudi Arabia among other countries. Saudi Arabia is expected to overtake the UAE as the largest online shopping market in the GCC by 2020. (Rana & Sulphey, 2020; Alabdan, 2019).

Saudi Arabia has a single digit share of worldwide online retailing. But because of a variety of factors, 70 percent of the population is under the age of 35 years, high connectivity and advanced IT infrastructure, it is a lucrative market. E-commerce revenue in Saudi Arabia amounted to 13 billion dollars in 2015. Since 2010, e-commerce has become increasingly popular with Saudi youth, with one in every five people making purchases using the Internet. However, the vast majority of KSA's population chooses to buy products from brick-and-mortar stores because of their lack of trust in online retailers (Abanmi, 2015). In particular, the factors influencing online consumer performance are critical for understanding and interpreting the online shopping process. More online retailers are emerging with increasing e-commerce sales. In businesses this dynamic shift from a brick and mortar to a click and dead model has led to numerous changes in businesses, such as increased user numbers, geographic scope, purchase volumes etc (Alabdan, 2019). As a result, in order to promote online shopping, companies are continuing to advance their transaction methods on the e-commerce platform-cash payments have been replaced by E-P (Kabir et al., 2015; Abrazhevich, 2004).

Many companies face a significant challenge in transitioning from traditional paper-based money transfers to a modern electronic payment system. Electronic payment, in general, can be described as a platform for making payments for goods and services purchased online through the internet (Abanmi, 2015; Abrazhevich, 2004; Widayat et al., 2020). In the meantime, consumers are faced with a rise in the number of online shopping from any e-tailer. It is an important concern to protect customer information and transaction data. Government agencies have a responsibility in particular to promote and facilitate healthy e-commerce in countries (Cheraghi et al., 2015). It should be noted that Saudi Arabia customers prefer to pay for cash delivery because of a lack of trust in payment methods online, such as credit cards (Alabdan, 2019). In 2004 the SADAD (SAMA) put in place the financial system for payment of bills electronically and the transfer of funds into the Kingdom and the Co-operation Council of the Kingdom of the Gulf (GCC). As a national electronic bill presentment and payment (EBPP) mechanism for the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Alkhowaiter, 2020), SADAD allows Saudi consumers to pay bills, purchase airline and bus tickets, and make payment transfers for online transactions. A few significant studies have looked into how this E-P system affects people's online shopping habits. As a result, the focus of this research is on how Saudi consumers are embracing SADAD as an E-P system.

Perceived Security

Perceived protection refers to a customer's subjective assessment of a system's security and how well they are secured from future threats (Linck et al., 2006). Users are more likely to reject E-P transactions if the system's perceived security is extremely poor, according to Tsiakis &

Sthephanides, (2005). Consumers who believe payment cards are highly secure, on the other hand, are more likely to use them than cash. Furthermore, according to a study conducted by Arango et al., (2014) among Canadian consumers, cash is more likely to be used as a preferred payment method than payment card due to a lack of trust in security and the fear of POS system fraud. Teoh et al., (2013) went on to say that an increase in device security incidents may have a negative impact on customer interest in E-P instruments. However, other studies by Ching & Hayashi, (2010) and Jusoh & Jing, (2019) on incorporating perceived security as a descriptive variable through payment instruments found that perceived security had no impact on the intention to use E-P. The following hypothesis is suggested based on previous literature:

H1. There is a significant relationship between perceived security and consumers' acceptance toward E-P.

Subjective Norm

Individuals' expectations of how most of the people they consider essential or with whom they have a close relationship will think about whether they should conduct a certain action are referred to as subjective norms (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977) (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Park et al., 2006). According to Ravi et al., (2007), subjective standard has a positive association with customer intentions to use retail banking services. In the context of Saudi Arabia, a study was conducted by Soomro, (2019) to analyses the factors influencing bank consumers' adoption of internet banking, and his findings suggest that there is a positive relationship between subjective norms and internet banking adoption. Subjective standards have been shown to be more effective and influential when it comes to attracting new and future adopters (Nasir et al., 2015; Alkhowaiter, 2020; Rana & Sulphay, 2020). This is due to a lack of self-experience among inexperienced and prospective adopters and consumers, who have a propensity to rely on others' advice and knowledge before implementing an innovation. The following hypothesis is derived from the discussion:

H2. There is a significant relationship between subjective norm and consumers' acceptance toward E-P.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is described by social cognitive theory as a person's self-perceptions of his ability to effectively carry out a specific behavior (Bandura, 1986). Furthermore, Bandura (1986) claims that one's understanding of one's abilities affects one's ability to complete a mission successfully. This is because people who are more confident in their abilities may perceive a job as being easier than those who are less confident. A person with high capability and self-efficacy will consider a new technology system to be easier to use and have a higher intention to fully implement it in the long run. Self-efficacy is described by social cognitive theory as a person's self-perceptions of his ability to effectively carry out a specific behaviour (Bandura, 1986).

According to Dinev et al., (2009) and Meuthia et al., (2020), new users with sufficient expertise and skills in technology systems are more optimistic and adaptable when interacting with

newly introduced systems. Soomro (2019) conducted research in Saudi Arabia to identify the factors influencing public sector employees' adoption of technology, with self-efficacy as one of the variables. The results show that self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on both the behavioural purpose to implement and the practical use of technology. This research also revealed that the positive effects of self-efficacy on technology acceptance are indirect, as they are influenced by the perceived utility and ease of use of the technology. The following hypothesis is formulated based on previous findings:

H3. There is a significant relationship between Self-efficacy and consumers' acceptance toward E-P.

Ease of use

Several studies have proven to be more useful when a technology is simple to use (Wang & Li, 2011; Davis, 1989; Shao et al., 2019). According to Flavian & Guinaliu, (2006), it is easier to use a computer system to promote confidence. This is because enhanced usability reduces the risk of error, which is crucial for the provision of financial services on the Internet. In addition, improved accessibility promotes reduced search costs (Bakos, 1997) and better understanding of the content and tasks of a website. As a consequence, Alsenaidy & Alsafdi, (2019) found that perceived convenience had a significant positive effect on the behavioural intention of Saudis to use online banking and thus, E-P. Customer interactivity is a key criterion for E-P delivery according to Ainscough & Lockett, (1996). Innovative user-friendly capabilities would attract users and not-users to the bank's website, Gerrard & Cunningham, (2003) say, by using various functions available on the website of the bank, such as interactive bond calculators, exchange rate converters and mortgage calculators. After a lengthy reaction period, a service delivery break often leads to customers asking if the transaction is finished or not (Alkhowaiter, 2020; Flavian & Guinaliu, 2006). For these reasons, Ching & Hayashi, (2010) concludes that a successful user-centered design of E-P systems is critical to gaining users' acceptance. For these reasons, Ching & Hayashi, (2010) concludes that a successful user-centered design of E-P systems is critical to attracting users' acceptance of E-P. In short, material, design, bank image and management, and pace are all important factors that affect consumers' perceptions of E-P systems due to perceived ease of use. It is suggested that the following hypothesis be tested:

H4. There is a significant relationship between ease of use and consumers' acceptance toward E-P.

Trust

The results of trust reduces the perceived risk, leading to positive E-P intentions (Yousafzai et al., 2003; Zhou, 2011). In previous studies, customers were influenced by confidence in e-commerce operations and participation in online money transfers (Soomro, 2019; Alzoubi, 2016; Jusoh & Jing, 2019; Rana & Sulphrey, 2020). In fact, the trust behind buyer-seller transactions has long been the driving force for customers with high expectations of successful exchange connections (Widayat et al., 2020). Many researchers therefore believe that the trust that affects critical to understand interpersonal behaviour and economic transactions, which influences customers' perceptions of E-P systems (Abanmi, 2015; Flavian & Guinaliu, 2006) and, as a result,

their adoption performance (Widayat et al., 2020; Zhou, 2011). The confidence of customers in an online environment becomes crucial since there is no assurance that the online seller will not engage in unwanted, unethical or opportunistic activities such as unfair pricing, incorrect information, distribution of personal data or buying activities, without prior consent (Shao et al., 2019). In most online transactions, trust is particularly important in E-P s because of the great level of ambiguity and risk (Zhou, 2011) . That is why trust is more important than security, according to (Kim et al., 2009). According to Kniberg, users and retailers are more likely to use a confidential company's unreliable payment system than a stable company payment system. It can therefore be concluded that confidence is critical to the success of electronic payments (Shao, 2019). It will be extremely difficult for E-P to gain widespread adoption without an appropriate infrastructure that users can trust (Kim et al., 2009). As a result, the following theory emerges:

H5. There is a significant relationship between consumers' trust and acceptance toward E-P.

Benefits

Chou et al., (2004) describe benefits as a major factor in acceptance and use of the electronic payment system. Eastin, (2002) also concluded that four e-commerce behaviour predicts adoption decisions before adoption in terms of perceived convenience and financial benefit (online shopping, banking, saving, and E-P systems). Widayat et al., (2020) states that reduced fixed and transaction costs include the economic benefits perceived from E-P. Cost of installation of payment machines, including card readers and software, while costs of transaction shall be borne by consumers and retailers whenever a transaction is performed (Chou et al., 2004). This will allow consumers to benefit from cheap online purchases because they have to pay their banks a small fee only for the services they use (Alkhowaiter, 2020; Sonia et al., 2012; Jusoh & Jing, 2019). Other key benefits of E-P include time and cost savings, as well as the convenient means of payment that users can use, store and transport the value of money through payment systems (Teoh et al., 2013). However, it still remains to be seen whether E-P saves time or money. The implementation of E-P can be expensive for studying how to use the Internet and new technologies, according to Kim et al, (2009). The following hypothesis is put forward to assess whether advantages are a critical determinant of consumers' perceptions of E-P:

H6. There is a significant relationship between benefit and consumers' acceptance toward E-P.

Consumers' Acceptance towards E-Payment

Product and service adoption can be explained in terms of execution, habit, application, or fulfilment, according to Liu & Guo, (2008). Many researchers have discovered that real adoption is difficult to calculate precisely on its own (Schuitema et al., 2013), and as a result, most studies on technology or innovation have looked at intention as a predictor of adoption (Shao et al., 2019; Meuthia et al., 2020). Since actual behavior is found to be explicitly and closely influenced by behavioral intention (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977), behavioural intention is considered a predictor of actual behavior. Since actual behavior is found to be explicitly and closely influenced by behavioral intention (Fishbein & Ajzen, 197), behavioral intention is considered a predictor of

actual behaviour. According to Fishbein & Ajzen, (1977), aim is expected to play a critical role in regulating the motivational factors that influence actual behavior. According to Fishbein & Ajzen, (1977), the better the intention to deal with the behavior, the more likely it is that the behavior will be carried out. In order to investigate mobile internet adoption in Japan, Kim et al., (2009) used intention, while Yu, (2012) used intention to investigate mobile commerce adoption among Saudi Arabian consumers. Behavioral purpose was also used by (Schöndienst et al., 2011) and Widayat et al., (2020) as a predictor of real microblogging adoption among businesses. Based on a thorough analysis of the literature, In order to better test E-P adoption respondents, the intention to adopt E-P will be used as the key dependent variable in this analysis.

Actual Usage of E-Payment

Since the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and other related theories often assess technology acceptance in terms of device use, the terms actual use and acceptance are often used interchangeably. TPB, on the other hand, suggests that intention is the proximal predictor of actual behavior (Davis, 1989), while Fishbein & Ajzen (1977) explain that when intentions and behavior are evaluated at the same level of precision, they are assumed to be strongly associated. Shih & Huang, (2009) used TAM to investigate the relationship between behavioral intention and actual use in the context of enterprise resource planning implementation, and their results revealed that the intention aroused leads to actual use. In addition, previous research has found empirical support for the connection between behavioral purpose and actual use of information systems (Vatanasakdakul et al., 2010). The following hypothesis is proposed based on these discussions:

H7. There is a significant relationship between consumers' acceptance toward E-P and actual usage of E-P.

The research structure for this analysis is shown in Figure 1. The six independent variables are thought to have a significant relationship with the dependent variable, which is the acceptance of E-P by customers. Following that, the relationship between customer acceptance of E-P and real E-P use is investigated. The methodology used is described in the following section.

Figure 1. Research framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Market adoption of E-P was investigated in this study. The study objectives are determined using an observational survey approach for collecting data through personal transmission and e-mail. In this study, quantitative statistics and questionnaire analyses were used. The survey instrument is divided into two sections. In the first chapter, personal and demographic data is given. The related studies have been conducted and reviewed in the second section of the survey questionnaire. Item scales with slight adjustments to adapt to the Saudi Arabian market background. Just a small percentage of those who have used E-P say they use services available in banks, at home, or at work, with just a small percentage saying they use E-P services at colleges. This is simple to understand since E-P allows users to conduct financial transactions whenever and wherever they choose. Respondents who use E-P at banks must use the devices to complete such tasks, such as paying credit card bills via the cash deposit machine and/or depositing checks. Network/internet-based E-P systems are used by the majority of respondents, followed by ATMs and cell phones. From the 850 questionnaires distributed, 431 questionnaires were originally collected for input. Because of a lack of data or invalid responses, 25 of the questionnaires were subsequently removed. In the end, 406 questionnaires were used in the analytical analysis.

Survey Instrument

A self-administered questionnaire was used to conduct the survey, which is divided into two parts. Section A consists of ten questions designed to gather demographic data. The independent and dependent variables are measured using 29 statements in Section B. The variables of the sample, the number of items used, and the studies from which they were adapted are all shown in Table 1. The research uses a five-point Likert scale with no middle point, ranging from 1strongly disagree to 5strongly agree. The five-point Likert scale is used to reduce social desirability bias (Garland, 1991) and encourage more people to react positively (Worcester & Burns, 1975).

Factors	Items	Adapted from
Perceived security	2	Kim et al.,2009; Teoh et al., 2013
Subjective norm	5	Davis, 1989; Jusoh & Jing, 2019
Self-efficacy	3	Davis, 1989; Luarn and Lin, 2005
Ease of use	2	Davis, 1989; Rana & Sulphrey, 2020
Trust	4	Kim et al.,2009
Benefits	5	Kim et al.,2009; Teoh et al., 2013
Consumers' acceptance towards E-P	4	Davis, 1989; Jusoh & Jing, 2019

Actual usage of E-P	4	Davis, 1989; Jusoh & Jing, 2019
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Reliability and validity

The content and construct validity of the measurement instrument used in this analysis were both assessed. Consultation with academics in the sector, consultation with seasoned clinicians, and pilot testing of the questionnaire were all part of the content validity test. The construct validity monitoring was carried out in two stages. The one-dimensionality and reliability of each research factor, as well as the goodness of fit to the proposed research model, were assessed. Using explanatory factor analysis and the principal component analysis process, the one-dimensionality of the study factors was investigated. Furthermore, the statistical measure "Cronbach alpha" was used to estimate the reliability of these variables. The scales used were found to be accurate and consistent in all tests. Table of contents (2).

Factors	KMO	Bartlett's test of sphericity	Eigen-value	Total variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Perceived security	0.779	104.12*	1.453	75.14	0.904
Subjective norm	0.835	80.65*	2.312	80.21	0.942
Self-efficacy	0.759	83.56*	2.119	67.68	0.954
Ease of use	0.865	115.43*	2.323	63.55	0.887
Trust	0.812	112.13*	2.653	79.41	0.890
Benefits	0.721	87.54*	1.918	77.32	0.851
Consumers' acceptance towards E-P	0.781	119.92*	2.557	73.15	0.920
Actual usage of E-P	0.711	89.95*	1.754	70.45	0.963

RESULTS

The results of several regressions involving both independent and dependent variables can be seen in Table 3. Given the objective and hypotheses of the study, several regression analyses are used. For all variables, the variation inflation factor (VIF) value is less than 10. This reduces multi-collinearity and allows the variables to be used for regression analyses (Chatterjee et al., 2000; Klein Baum et al., 1988). Benefits, ease of use and auto efficiency are strongly linked to the perception of E-P s by consumers, with an R2 value of 75.1 percent. However, protection and trust do not significantly affect the consumer's attitudes towards E-P. H1 and H5 are therefore not suitable.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.742 ^a	0.711	0.751	0.06620

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	.436	.081		6.558	0.000		
Perceived security	.093	.111	.336	7.570	0.402	0.731	1.124
Subjective norm	.431	.131	.187	4.510	0.012	0.774	1.321
Self-efficacy	.385	.107	.521	6.541	0.000	0.825	1.354
Ease of use	.414	.101	.522	6.545	0.001	0.845	1.214
Trust	.324	.025	.481	6.234	0.512	0.733	1.115
Benefits	.345	.035	.505	7.871	0.011	0.816	1.345

Pearson correlation coefficient is used to establish a connection between consumers' acceptance of E-P and their actual use of E-P. As shown in Table, the results are optimistic and important in the relationship between customer acceptance of E-P and real E-P use (4).

		Actual usage		
Acceptance	r	0.580*		
	Sig.	0.000		
	N	406		

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, current research offers detailed understandings of the intention to adopt E-P in the sense of Saudi consumers based on perceived protection, subjective standard, self-efficacy, ease of use, confidence, and benefits. Many of the study's general and particular goals were met at the conclusion. The highest correlation and b-values equate to a gain. Gain is a major driver of E-P adoption, according to previous studies (Alhanoof & Othman, 2018; Alsenaidy & Alsafdi, 2019; Alkhowaiter, 2020). Sumanjeet reports that people have a greater capacity to pay taxes, allowances, penalties, fines and transactions with E-P at unorthodox locations (2009). Sumanjeet (2009) has found that E-P s provide greater flexibility for people to pay in an unusual place and at any time of day, 365 days a year, taxes and allowances, penalties and fines. As the easy-to-use aspect is linked to the consumer's E-P perceptions, the result is extremely important. The results of previous investigations (Zhou, 2011; Yu, 2012; Widayat et al., 2020) showed that E-P platforms are easy to use, with a simple content and structure. As a consequence, they have found it easy to learn how to use E-P. The coefficient of correlation and b-values for independence are strong implying that self-efficacy is a further important factor that affects Saudi E-P behavior. As most respondents have previously used E-P , their positive experiences encourage them to continue using it, says Bandura (1986) and Eastin (2002). The results of the research (statistically confirmed positive relations between subjective standards and E-P intention) suggest that consumers are

easily influenced by their neighbors in adopting E-P s based on a subjective standard. E-P providers should carry out in-depth customer reviews and make regular changes as required, as word of mouth and positive feedback from those who are closest to the individual can significantly affect the decisions of future users. E-P provider should conduct thoroughness analysis of customer reviews and regularly make amendments, which could have a significant effect on future users' decision to use an E-P system, as well as on the word of mouth and constructive feedback of individuals.

Although protection has not been identified as a significant factor. The outcome contradicts previous research (Alsenaidy & Alsafdi, 2019; Meuthia et al., 2020). Consumers are gradually accepting the measures taken by many banking institutions and online transaction facility providers to resolve the challenges associated with protection, implying that Saudis do not consider security to be a significant problem. Users will receive daily warnings from online transaction facility providers, as well as updates on any fraud incidents. Trust, like protection, has not been found to be significantly related to customer perceptions of E-P. Previous research (Kim et al., 2009; Leong et al., 2019) found that trust is only moderately or not associated with the intention to operate online. This could be clarified by the interest of users in the security systems of banking and other online transaction providers. In addition, important coefficients were discovered between E-P acceptance by E-P consumers and actual E-P use.

The factors that influence Saudi consumers' perceptions of E-P are investigated in this report. The findings show that E-P is commonly used, indicating that such services are becoming more common in Saudi Arabia. Four variables are strongly correlated with customers' perceptions of E-P, according to the regression findings. Surprisingly, consumers' attitudes toward E-P are not substantially influenced by protection or confidence. As a result, both security and trust are worthy of further investigation. In future research, a greater sample size across various geographical areas should be considered to improve precision and generalizability of the results. Because the perceptual usefulness of a technology is determined by its perceived ease of use, future studies should take into account perceived usefulness and other variables such as anonymity, convertibility, efficiency, reliability, traceability, and applicability (Alhanoof & Othman, 2018).

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